

Electroanalytical characteristics of Zn-enoxacin complex

Lizeng Wang^{a*}, Zesheng An^a, Jianquan Wang^a, Xiaoli Zhang^a and Hailan Huang^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Shandong University, Jinan, 250100, P. R. China

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Qingdao Normal College, Qingdao, 266300, P. R. China

Manuscript received 10 July 2000, accepted 3 January 2001

The electroanalytical characteristics of Zn-enoxacin complex are described. The overall stability constant of the 1 : 2 Zn-enoxacin complex is calculated in B-R buffer of pH 9.6. The reduction peak potential of the complex is -1.19 V (vs SCE). The linear concentration of Zn^{II} is 2.0×10^{-8} to 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm⁻³ and the detection limit 7.7×10^{-10} mol dm⁻³. The reduction mechanism of the complex is proposed.

Enoxacin [1-ethyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid], a quinolone derivative, is used in the therapy of infections and shows great activity against Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria¹. Enoxacin has been determined by HPLC², UV-VIS spectrophotometry³, high performance capillary electro-phoresis⁴ and polarographic and voltammetric techniques^{5,6}. However, formation of the Zn-enoxacin complex and its characteristics have never been reported. The effectiveness of quinolone derivative drugs can be reduced obviously when taken with other medicines containing metal ions. Also quinolone derivatives affect trace metal metabolism, being potent inhibitors of some Cu and Zn dependent enzymes⁷. In view of the above reasons, investigation on the Zn-enoxacin complex was undertaken.

Results and Discussion

The effect of pH on the peak current was investigated in B-R buffer of different pHs 3–12. At pH around 9.6, the peak current was found higher and more stable, so this pH was chosen. Potential affected the peak current greatly. When initially potentially increased or terminal potential decreased, the peak current increased until initial and terminal potential reached -0.7 and -1.6 V, respectively, where the shape of the peak became distorted. So the scan potential was chosen between -0.7 and -1.6 V.

Enoxacin

Under the above conditions, peaks of second derivative for enoxacin ($E_p = -1.175$ V, curve 3), and Zn-enoxacin mixture ($E_p = -1.19$ V, curve 4) were obtained (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Second derivative single-sweep voltammogram of Zn-enoxacin complex : (1) B-R buffer (pH 9.6), (2) B-R buffer (pH 9.6) + 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ Zn^{II} , (3) B-R buffer (pH 9.6) + 5.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ enoxacin, (4) B-R buffer (pH 9.6) + 5.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ enoxacin + 1.0×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³ Zn^{II} ; accumulation time (t_a) = 90 s, scan rate = 250 mV s⁻¹.

There is no peak for Zn^{II} in the potential range chosen. With the increase of the concentration of enoxacin and Zn^{II} , the peak current of Zn-enoxacin mixture increased, which indicates the formation of Zn-enoxacin complex. Because, by using the second derivative method, the peaks

Fig. 2. Repetitive cyclic voltammogram of Zn-enoxacin complex : 5.0×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} enoxacin + 5.0×10^{-7} mol dm^{-3} Zn^{II} in B-R buffer (pH 9.6); accumulation time (t_a) = 90 s, rest time = 10 s, scan rate = 100 mV s^{-1} .

of Zn-enoxacin complex were higher and the peak shape was more narrow, thus the peaks were more sensitive than those of the normal method.

At a DME, the relationship between the peak current and the concentration of Zn^{II} was investigated. When enoxacin concentration was fixed (5.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}), the peak current was linearly proportional to the concentration of Zn^{2+} in the range 2.0×10^{-8} to 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm^{-3} . The detection limit was 7.7×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3} . The equation of the calibration graph for Zn^{II} is $y = 0.5x + 1.5$, where y is the peak current (μA) and x the concentration of Zn^{II} (mol dm^{-3}). The correlation coefficient $r = 1.00$ ($n = 9$) shows excellent linearity.

Composition of the Zn-enoxacin complex : When the concentration of Zn^{II} was fixed, different peak current was obtained with the change of enoxacin concentration according to the equation⁸,

$$\frac{1}{i} = \frac{1}{i_{\text{max}}} + \frac{1}{i_{\text{max}} \beta} \frac{1}{[\text{enoxacin}]^n}$$

The plot of $1/i$ vs $1/[\text{enoxacin}]^n$ showed that when $n = 2$, a straight line was obtained. So the complex was believed to be formed by one molecule of Zn^{II} with two molecules of enoxacin. The overall stability constant β was calculated to be $\log \beta = 11.22$.

Adsorptive characteristics of the complex : The electrocapillary curve showed that Zn-enoxacin complex was adsorbed on the DME; the surface tension of the DME decreased in the presence of 5.0×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} enoxacin. After the addition of Zn^{II} (1.0×10^{-6} mol dm^{-3}), the reduction of the surface tension was greater than that of only enoxacin.

As can be seen from the repetitive cyclic voltammogram (Fig. 2), there are only reduction peaks on the

cathodic branches, but no corresponding oxidation peaks are observed on the anodic ones. This means that the reduction process is irreversible. The peak current is obviously smaller in the subsequent repetitive scan cycles, which indicates that it is the reactant that is adsorbed on the DME.

The dependence of the peak current on the scan rate also demonstrates that the complex has adsorptive characteristics. When the rest time was definite, at low concentrations of Zn^{II} and enoxacin, the peak current was linearly proportional to the scan rate; when concentrations were high, the peak current was proportional to the square-root of the scan rate. The accumulation time was 90 s, rest time 10 s. When the scan rate increased from 50 to 500 mV s^{-1} , the peak potential shifted negatively to 60 mV, which indicates that the reduction process is irreversible⁹ and the species adsorbed on the DME is the reductant¹⁰.

The peak current increased with the accumulation time t_a ; when t_a was greater than 100 s, the peak current became stable. The effect of t_a on the peak current shows that the complex can be adsorbed on the DME until the adsorption and desorption equilibrium is set up.

Reduction mechanism : The effect of pH on the peak potential was carried out. As pH increased, the peak potential shifted in the negative direction, which indicates that hydrogen ions are involved in the reduction process. So we can propose that it is the enoxacin in the complex that is reduced. According to earlier literature⁶, two protons and two electrons are involved in the reduction process of enoxacin. Thus we can reasonably suggest that there are four protons and four electrons involved in the reduction process of Zn-enoxacin complex, because one complex consists of two enoxacins. The reduction mechanism of Zn-enoxacin complex is shown as : $\text{Zn}^{2+} + 2 \text{ enoxacin} \rightarrow \text{Zn}^{2+} \cdot (\text{enoxacin})_2 \rightarrow \text{Zn}^{\text{II}} \cdot (\text{enoxacin})_2(\text{ads}) + 4 e + 4 \text{ H}^+ \rightarrow \text{Zn}^{2+} + 2 \text{ H}_2(\text{enoxacin})$.

Experimental

A Jinan JP3-1 (China) oscillopolarograph (drop time 7 s, scan rate 250 mV s^{-1}) with a dropping mercury electrode (DME) as working electrode, a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode and a platinum plate as counter electrode was used to record single-sweep polarograms. A Jinan 79-1 (China) voltammetric analyzer coupled with a LZ3-204 X-Y recorder (Shanghai Dahua Instrument Factory, China) and another three-electrode system (a hanging drop mercury electrode (HDME) as working electrode, a SCE reference electrode and a platinum plate as counter electrode) was used to investigate adsorption characteristics of the complex.

All chemicals were of A.R. grade and triple-distilled water was used throughout. Enoxacin (Sanxing Chemical Corporation, Jinan, China) stock solution (1.0×10^{-3} mol dm^{-3}) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of

enoxacin in 0.2 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide. Zn^{II} stock solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was prepared by dissolving metal zinc in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} sulfuric acid and then diluted to 0.1 dm^3 with water. B-R buffer was prepared by mixing 0.4 mol dm^{-3} boric, orthophosphoric and acetic acids with 0.2 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide.

Procedure : A mixture of B-R buffer (pH 9.6; 0.002 dm^3), enoxacin solution ($0.001 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and appropriate amount of Zn^{II} solution was placed in the detection cell, then diluted to 0.02 dm^3 and the pH adjusted to 9.6 with 1.0 mol dm^{-3} sodium hydroxide solution. After deoxygenation with purified nitrogen for 10 min, a negative-going scan (-0.7 to -1.6 V) was initiated. The experiment was carried out at room temperature.

References

1. J. Joos, B. Ledergerber, M. Flep, S. D. Bettex, R. Luthy and W. Siegenthaler, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1985, **27**, 353; J. Smith, *Pharm. J.*, 1984, **233**, 299; K. Sato, Y. Inoue, T. Fujii, H. Aoyama and M. Inoue, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1986, **30**, 777.
2. Y. P. Qin, D. R. Liang, M. Z. Liang, D. Y. Lui, L. Yu, Y. G. Zhou, and Z. Zeng, *Yaowu Fenxi Zazhi*, 1992, **12**, 277; T. B. Veer and A. M. Baar, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1985, **343**, 449; L. O. White, H. M. Bowyer, C. H. McMullin and K. Desai, *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.*, 1988, **21**, 512; K. J. Goebel and H. Stolz, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1991, **14**, 753; D. Marini and G. Pollino, *Boll. Chim. Farm.*, 1987, **126**, 336; S. P. Zhai, M. R. Korrapati, X. X. Wei, S. Muppalla and R. E. Vestal, *J. Chromatogr. (B), Biomed. Appl.*, 1995, **669**, 372; H. P. Cao and W. Z. Liu, *Yaowu Fenxi Zazhi*, 1993, **13**, 181; R. Jain and C. L. Rain, *LC-GC*, 1992, **10**, 707.
3. H. P. Zhang, Q. S. Kang and Z. D. Huang, *Yaowu Fenxi Zazhi*, 1992, **12**, 50; A. Z. Du and W. Z. Liu, *Yaowu Fenxi Zazhi*, 1990, **10**, 356.
4. C. Yin and Y. T. Wu, *Yaowu Fenxi Zazhi*, 1997, **17**, 371.
5. J. A. Squella, A. Alvaez-Lueje, J. C. Sturm and L. J. Nunez-Vergara, *Anal. Lett.*, 1993, **26**, 1943.
6. G. R. Zhou, H. Z. Fan and J. H. Pan, *Analyst*, 1995, **120**, 2237; Z. Q. Zhang, Y. F. Li, X. M. He and H. Zhang, *Talanta*, 1996, **43**, 635.
7. J. Wagner, P. Vitali, J. Schoun and E. Giroux, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1977, **55**, 408.
8. L. Naqiang and G. Xiaoxia, *Fenxi Huaxue*, 1974, **2**, 459.
9. F. Anson, "Electrochemistry and Electroanalytical Chemistry", Beijing University Press, China, 1983, pp. 14-16.
10. A. M. Bond "Modern Polarographic Methods in Analytical Chemistry", Marcel Dekker, New York 1980, p. 196.